

A Future Disrupted - Big Data, Deep Learning, Intelligent Machines, And Our Life With Artificial Intelligence

Everywhere, around the world, Artificial Intelligence (AI) continues to reshape organizations, industries, and entire societies. The way that businesses operate in many fields continues to be disrupted by the emergence of many disruptive technologies that can see, think, feel, and predict. Despite this, with this new exciting emergence, there continues to be many questions that businesses and individuals face, including questioning the place that AI will have in our world, the value that it will unlock, and how organizations and their people start the AI journey.

In this keynote session, Nathaniel Payne, a global technology and business leader and artificial intelligence researcher, will talk about the future of artificial intelligence, as well as how the sub fields of data science, cloud computing, and deep learning are forcing businesses to re-consider how they do businesses, and societies to re-think how they live. He will discuss the new emergent technology breakthroughs in the space that can be leveraged today, the technologies that will change industries tomorrow, as well as how organizations tactically begin on the Artificial Intelligence journey. This includes understanding the elements needed to embed AI and machine learning within an organization, the optimal organizational structures that enable organizations to unleash the power of AI and aided-intelligence, as well as the disciplines poised to accelerate the spread of AI technology in organization's around the world. He will also talk about how organization's in many disciplines can leverage AI and data for competitive advantage, thus improving their bottom line.

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